

Physico-Chemical Investigation on Thiomalate Complex of Thallium (I)

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Potentiometric and conductometric studies of the complex formed by Thallium (I) with Thiomalic acid in aqueous medium of 0.1M KNO_3 reveal the formation of only one colourless 1 : 1 complex, predominating in the pH range 9.0–10.5. The stability constants of the complex formed were computed by Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method at three different temperatures. The log K values were found to be 3.58, 3.71 and 3.78 at 30°, 35°, and 40° respectively. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS calculated at 35° are –5.22 kcal/mole –5.75 kcal/mole and –1.7 k. cal/respectively.

Thiomalic acid containing an active -SH group, which is α to one -COOH group and β to another -COOH group, has been reported to form complexes with some metals,^{1,2}. Recently F.B. Martinez and coworkers³ have also used it for the detection and determination of Fe, Mo, U, etc. There is, however, no information available in the literature regarding the complexing tendency of Thiomalic acid with Tl(I). Hence the present investigation has been initiated. The composition and stability constant of the complex have been studied by potentiometric and conductometric methods. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have also been evaluated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiomalic acid (99.8% Evan's Chemetics, Inc., New York) and A-nala-R (BDH) reagents TlNO_3 , KNO_3 , NaOH, etc. were used and their solutions were prepared in double distilled air free conductivity water. Freshly prepared solutions of the reagents were always used with a view to avoid the effects of age and hydrolysis.

A Cambridge bench pattern (null deflection type) pH-meter was used for pH-measurements. A glass electrode of 0.14 pH range calibrated frequently by using buffer solutions of different pH values was used in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by low resistance salt bridge. All the pH-titrations were carried out in aqueous medium of 0.1M KNO_3 . The temperatures were controlled by an electrically maintained thermostat.

The conductance measurements were carried out by means of an electronic eye type conductometer (L.B.R., W.T.W., Germany).

1. I. M. Klotz and co-workers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 2920.
2. G. R. Lenz and A. E. Martell, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**(3), 378.
3. F. B. Martinez, M. Carman and M. Mourino, *Inform. quim. Anal.* (Madrid), 1964, **18**, 20, 28.

The experimental procedure consists in performing a series of pH and conductometric titrations of Thiomalic acid with standard NaOH in absence and presence of Tl (I) at various ligand to metal ratios. The Calvin and Melchior's⁴ extension of Bjerrum's⁵ method was used to calculate the stability constant of the complex formed. The typical reproducible results obtained out of the large number experiments performed are shown in Figs. 1—3.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stoichiometry :—In order to establish the stoichiometry of the complex formed during the interaction of $TlNO_3$ and TMA (Thiomalic acid), the extent of proton displacement was determined by titrating solutions containing TMA and $TlNO_3$ in different ratios against standard alkali.

Fig.1 represents the pH and conductometric titrations of solutions $6.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ in TMA (curves 1 & 4), $6.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ in TMA and $6.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ in $TlNO_3$ (curves 2 & 5), $6.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ in TMA and $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ $TlNO_3$ (curve 3) with $0.2 M$ NaOH. The abscissa represents the moles of NaOH added per mole of ligand 'a'.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric (curves 1—3) and conductometric (curves 4 & 5) Titrations of TMA in absence and presence of Tl(I) with $0.2 M$ NaOH.
 Curves 1 & 4— $6.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ TMA.
 Curves 2 & 5— $6.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ TMA + $6.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ $TlNO_3$
 Curve 3 — $6.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ TMA + $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ $TlNO_3$

The appearance of only one inflection (fig. 1, curve 1) after two moles of base/mole of ligand have been added corresponding to the complete neutralisation of two carboxyl hydrogens in a single step. Hence if free TMA having three replaceable hydrogen ions is denoted as H_3SA , the reaction between 'a' interval of 0-2, may be represented in a single step by the equation.

The absence of an inflection at $a=1$, indicates that the acidities of both the hydrogens are fairly comparable in magnitude and that the three ligand species H_3SA , H_2SA^- and HSA^{-2} exist in equilibrium in the pH range corresponding to the values of 'a' from 0-2. Addition of an equimolar concentration of $Tl(I)$, (fig. 1, curve 2) alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve as a result of complex formation. It is seen that the first buffer region of these two curves coincides till two moles of $NaOH$ /mole of ligand have been added. Since the extent of the proton displacement depends on the relative affinities of the ligand for hydrogen ion and the metal ion; the coincidence of the first buffer region in the 'a' interval of 0-2, indicates that the affinity of $Tl(I)$ for the ligand is not great enough to compete with the relatively high concentration of hydrogen ions in acidic pH range. Consequently $Tl(I)$ is not appreciably bound to the ligand till both the carboxyl hydrogens have been neutralised. However, the lowering of the buffer regions between $a=2$ and $a=3$ (where a single proton of sulphhydryl group is bound to the ligand anion) and their subsequent overlapping is indicative of the formation of 1 : 1 $Tl(I)$ complex as a result of the displacement of sulphhydryl proton. Since the displacement reaction

occurs only when it is assisted through the maintaining of relatively high pH , it is apparent that the $Tl(I)$ ion is only bound to the mercaptide ion of the ligand.

The relative lowering of buffer regions, when a solution containing 1 : 2 ratio of $Tl(I)$ to TMA was titrated, (fig. 1, curve 3), further confirms the formation of a weak 1 : 1 complex.

Further evidence for the formation of 1 : 1 complex and the replacement of proton by $Tl(I)$ from $-SH$ group has been obtained by titrating Di. Sod. Thiomalate in absence and presence of $Tl(I)$ against standard alkali.

Conductometric studies : Fig. 1 (curves 4 & 5) represents the changes in conductance when solution of TMA was titrated against $NaOH$ in absence and presence of $Tl(I)$. In such conductometric titrations, where the weak acid was neutralised by a strong base, the shape of the titration curves depends on the concentrations and dissociation constants of the acid. The curves show a minimum, because when $NaOH$ is added progressively to a solution of TMA, the salt formed during the first part of the reaction tends to repress the ionisation of the acid still present so that its conductance decreases. The rising salt concentration will, however, tend to increase the conductance, owing

to these opposing influences, the titration curves show a minimum. As the titration proceeds, break at $a=2$ (fig. 1; curve 4) was obtained and beyond which the graph becomes linear. Fig. 1, curve 5 for a solution containing TMO and TINA_3 in the ratio of 1 : 1, shows two breaks at $a=2$ and $a=3$ corresponding to the neutralisation

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titrations of TMA in absence and presence of Tl(I) with 0.2M NaOH .
 Curves 1, 3 & 5— $3.0\text{ ml M KNO}_3 + 4.0\text{ ml M/20 TMA}$ (Total—Vol. 30.0 ml) at 30° , 35° and 40° respectively.
 Curves 2, 4 & 6— $3.0\text{ ml M KNO}_3 + 4.0\text{ ml M/20 TMA} + 1.0\text{ ml M/20 TlNO}_3$ (Total volume 30.0 ml) at 30° , 35° and 40° respectively.

of two carboxyl hydrogens and the formation of TISA^{-2} as a result of the replacement of highly mobile H^+ from $-\text{SH}$ group with a less mobile Tl(I) ion respectively in accordance with the equation (2).

These results are similar to those obtained by potentiometric methods demonstrating the formation of a weak 1 : 1 complex.

Stability constant : The Calvin and Melchior's⁴ extension of Bjerrum's⁵ method was adopted to calculate the stability constant of Tl —Thiomalic acid complex from potentiometric data. A series of pH titrations were carried out between 0.2 M NaOH

4. M. Calvin and N. C Melchior, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3270.

5. J. Bjerrum, "Metal amine formation in aqueous solutions", P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1941.

and TMA in absence and presence of Tl(I) ion at three different temperatures (Fig. 3.)

Fig. 3. Plot of \bar{n} as a function of $-\log [SA^{-3}]$ at three different temperatures.

Curve 1. at 30°.

Curve 2. at 35°.

Curve 3. at 40°.

The evaluation of \bar{n} values was made from Fig. 3. At various pH values, the horizontal distances between curves 1–2, 3–4 and 5–6 (corresponding to 30° 35° & 40° respectively), measure quite accurately the additional base consumed or the total number of SA^{-3} complexed. The ratio of the horizontal distance between two curves to the total Tl(I) ion concentration is \bar{n} . At any pH , $[SA^{-3}]$ was calculated as

$$[SA^{-3}] = \frac{[H_2SA]_{\text{total}} - [TlSA^{-2}]}{\frac{[H^+]^3}{K_1 K_2 K_3} + \frac{[H^+]^2}{K_2 K_3} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_3}} + 1 \quad (3)$$

where K_1 ($pK_1 = 3.30$), K_2 ($pK_2 = 4.94$) and K_3 ($pK_3 = 10.64$) are the first, second and third dissociation constants of the acid. Thus a series of values of \bar{n} and $[SA^{-3}]$ at various pH values were obtained and formation curves were plotted. The approximate values of $\log K$ were read directly from the graph at $\bar{n} = 0.5$. These values of $\log K$ were used to calculate \bar{n} for known values of $[SA^{-3}]$. These calculated \bar{n} values were then plotted against $-\log [SA^{-3}]$, (Fig. 3, curves 1, 2 and 3 at 30°, 35° and 40° respectively). The final values of $\log K$ were determined from these curves and found to be 3.58, 3.71 and 3.78 at 30°, 35° and 40° respectively.

Thermodynamic functions: The values of the changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS accompanying the reaction have been evaluated at 35°.

The expression⁶

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K \quad (4)$$

relating stability constants K to the free energy change of the reaction was employed for evaluating the value of ΔG , which was found to be -5.22 Kcal/mole.

The value of ΔH was determined with the help of isobar equation⁶ given as follows :—

$$\frac{d \ln K}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H}{RT^2} \quad (5)$$

where T is the absolute temperature and R is the gas constant and may be more conveniently written in the form

$$\frac{d \log K}{d(1/T)} = \frac{\Delta H}{4.57} \quad (6)$$

The values of $\log K$ obtained at different temperatures were plotted as a function of $(1/T)$. The gradient of the tangent drawn at the point corresponding to 35° was determined and equated with $\frac{-\Delta H}{4.57}$. The value of ΔH thus obtained was found to be -5.75 Kcal/mole.

The entropy change (ΔS) of the reaction was calculated employing the equation⁶

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T} \quad (7)$$

and found to be -1.7 Cal/degree.

It is apparent from the above studies that the reaction between Thallium (I) and Thiomalic acid results in the formation of a weak complex containing the reactants in the ratio of 1 : 1. The values of stability constants found to be 3.58, 3.71 and 3.78 at 30° , 35° and 40° respectively, and those of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS , at 35° as -5.22 Kcal/mole, -5.75 Kcal/mole and -1.7 Cal/degree respectively.

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